

Ecology of biofouling community

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Abstract

Dapeng, located in the eastern part of ShenZhen, is an area recognized for its seafood cuisine. This location is home to several natural reserves, preserving unique ecosystems. The clear water there made it a preferable place to collect samples. In addition, as lying in a fault uplift zone, the rocky coasts occupy most of the coastal line of Dapeng Peninsula. Typical coastal erosion landforms such as sea cliffs, wave cut benches, sea caves, sea arches and sea stacks can thus often be found on the coasts [1]. Because of these factors, we went to Dapeng in ShenZhen. There, I collect biofouling communities at a fish-farm. I collected specimen from the biofouling community and performed PCR of COI gene for species identification. Nine specimens were collected, and the species identities of DP6H & DP7H, DP8H & DP9H and DP14H & DP15H specimens were determined by COI sequence respectively, including the gastropod *Polynoidae* sp. SS-2021, *Parhyale hawaiiensis* and *Thelepus japonicus*.

1. Introduction

Biofouling communities, also known as sessile marine invertebrate, have served as an important model in ecology for evaluating fundamental patterns and processes, including invasion dynamics, which vary at broad spatial and temporal scales [2]. They are also essential three-dimensional structure composed by small organisms. Therefore, the complexity of the biofouling communities largely contributes to the massive biodiversity. Biofouling communities are necessary despite their potential negative impact on marine ecosystems, infrastructure, and human activities [2]. The aims of this study are to discover the significance of biofouling communities in ecosystems and industries and identify the biodiversity within biofouling communities.

2. Methods

2.1. Sampling and preparation

Sample of biofouling communities was collected from fish weir at Dapeng, ShenZhen. After sampling, the sam-

ples were brought back to the laboratory with a plastic box. To preserve the inner environment and organisms of the community, an oxygen pump is placed in the plastic box.

2.2. Preparing specimens

After two days, the sample was picked out. Tweezers and small hammers were used to break the biofouling communities into pieces. The specimens that were found in the biofouling structure were put in culture dishes as containers. Then, the species were separated in new and different culture dishes based on the types of species they were. After finishing the classification of species, one specimens from each culture dish was picked to represent the type of species it belongs to. After that, each species was put in a single test tube. To solidify the shape and size of the species specimens, DNA extraction buffer was added to each tube. The test tubes were then put in a refrigerator to preserve the specimens.

2.3. Extracting DNA

The day after, the specimens were taken out from the refrigerator and were grinded into liquid with a glass homogenizer. After grinding, the lysis solution from BioFlux's Biospin Marine Animal Genomic DNA Extraction Kit was added into specimens. The mixture of lysis solution and specimen was moved into a 2mL centrifuge tube. Next, the processed specimens were put into Magnetic stirring pot in 50°C environment for 2 hours. After 2 hours, the centrifuge with the processed specimens were put on the centrifuge of 12000g for 3 minutes. Then, 500 μ L was supernatant from the mixture. 700 μ L Binding Buffer and 300 μ L anhydrous ethanol was added in the supernatant. The mixture was transferred into spin column when it was inverted. Afterward, the spin column was put on the centrifuge for 1 minute of 10000g. When the centrifugal process was

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complete, the waste liquid was poured away, and the PW Buffer was added into the mixture. The mixture experienced same centrifugal process as above. Then, the Wash Buffer was added into the mixture and was placed on the centrifuge in 10000g for 1 minute. This process was then repeated.

Since the spin column had experienced centrifuging for 1 minute of 10000g, it was transferred into a new 2mL centrifuge tube. The 50 μ L distilled water was added into the spin column and it needed to go through the same centrifugal process as described above. Finally, the purification of DNA was completed. The concentration of the extracted DNA for each specimen was measured by NanoDrop.

2.4. PCR amplification

The mitochondrial gene fragment encoding cytochrome c oxidase subunit (COI) was amplified by PCR. The PCR reaction mixture contains 10 μ L Phanta Max Master Mix (P525-AA) from Vazyme, 2 μ L of primer mixture of LCO 1490 (5' GGTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG 3') and HCO 2198 (5' TAAACTTCAGGGTGACCAAAAAATCA 3') and 500ng of the extracted DNA template's solution (volume of DNA template adjusted according to its concentration). The reaction was added up to 20 μ L by ddH₂O. The PCR program was as follows: 4 minutes at 94°C, 30 cycles of 30 seconds at 94°C, 30 seconds at 45°C, 30 seconds at 72°C, and 7 minutes at 72°C. 1% agarose gel was prepared by adding 0.25g of agarose from Blowest Agarose and 25mL TAE buffer (the buffer for electrophoresis) were mixed. The mixture was then put in the microwave oven for 2 minutes of 80°C. The heated mixture should point left most gel's bottom. After that, the DNA mixture was added. The mixture of the two liquids should be in the amount of 1 μ L. The gel electrophoresis started after the electric wires were connected. This process lasted for approximately 20 minutes.

2.5. Classification of species

As all the samples derived from the fouling complexes found in Dapeng, the samples were labelled as DPH. After receiving the DNA sequence codes, BioEdit Sequence Alignment Editor was used to trim the relatively stable part of the codes. The trimmed sequences were saved as a new document on Notepad. Blast (Basic Local Alignment Search Tool) on National Center for Biotechnology Information was used to identify the species the specimens belong to. All information was then recorded as is shown in Table 1.

3. Results

Figure 1 shows all the photos of the specimens we collected, which includes three crustacean (an amphipod, an isopod, a crab) and a tubeworm, a polychaete, and a peanut

worm.

By breaking open the biofouling structure, I found that these species were embedded in the gaps within the biofouling community. Brittle star specimens were collected within the dead shell of bivalve (Figure 2). When the specimen was moved out of the biofouling community, we discovered that it was afraid of light as it tended to hide from bright areas. Besides, other specimens, such as isopod and amphipod, fell out immediately after we broke the biofouling community. The specimens of polychaetes, which were annelid tubeworms and the two polychaetes, were either clustered together within the minute gaps between the biofouling community or were found when the polychaetes bind to the broken pieces of the biofouling community.

Using these specimens, we performed DNA extraction, PCR amplification of COI gene fragment, and DNA sequencing, to identify the species identity of each specimen identity of each specimen. Out of 9 specimens, the COI fragment of 3 specimens was successfully sequenced and used for species identification. Table 1 shows the results. Based on the results of BLASTx, we discovered that the LCO and HCO results of DP6H & DP7H are two types of polychaete: Polynoidae sp. SS-2021 and Lepidonotus squamatus; the LCO and HCO results of DP8H & DP9H are a species of amphipod: Parhyale hawaiiensis; the LCO and HCO results of DP14H & DP15H are 2 types of polychaetas: Thelepus japonicus, Polychaeta sp. BOLD:ACQ0473. Although we failed to run the results for the other 6 specimens, it is important to notice that the processes of DNA purification and extraction needed to be implemented with careful measures, making sure that there is no mixture of impurities.

4. Discussion

4.1. The Importance of biofouling communities

Biofouling communities create biodiversity, which allows various of species to live together. This is important as it reflects the fact that biofouling communities allow species interact with each other, and thus creating linkage between species, allow different species to be highly dependent on each other for survival. This is supported by the observation that many small marine invertebrates including brittle stars, crustaceans, polychaete tubeworms and polychaetes were found inside the minute gaps of the sampled biofouling structure.

4.2. tBLASTn vs. BLASTx

Blastx was used for result instead of tBLASTn as tBLASTn transfers protein into translated nucleotide while BLASTx transfers translated nucleotide to protein. This means that BLASTn is faster than BLASTx as it makes far fewer comparisons, and each comparison is more straightforward than BLASTx; On the contrary, BLASTn is more

Table 1. The species identification result for samples. (% ID to the matched sequence of the sequence obtained from sanger sequencing using the specified primer.)

Sample ID	Classification	Blastx_result*	Species
DP1H & DP2H	Brittle star	N/A	N/A
DP3H & DP4H	Isopod	N/A	N/A
DP5H	Tubeworm	N/A	N/A
DP6H & DP7H	Polychaete	LCO (99.03%) HCO (100%)	<i>Polynoidae</i> sp. SS-2021, <i>Lepidonotus squamatus</i>
DP8H & DP9H	Amphipod	LCO (99.44%) HCO(99.44%)	<i>Parhyale hawaiiensis</i>
DP10H & DP11H	Peanut worm	N/A	N/A
DP12H & DP13H	Crab	N/A	N/A
DP14H & DP15H	Polychaete	HCO(96.11%) LCO(98.82%)	<i>Thelepus japonicus</i> , <i>Polychaeta</i> sp. BOLD:ACQ0473
DP16H & DP17H	Polychaete	N/A	N/A

Figure 1. (A) DP1H: the sample of brittle star found in the fouling complex. (B) DP3H & DP4H: the sample of isopod found in the fouling complex. (C) DP5H: the sample of tubeworm found in the fouling complex. (D) DP6H & DP7H: the sample of polychaete found in the fouling complex. (E) DP8H & DP8H: the sample of amphipod found in the fouling complex. (F) DP10H & DP11H: the sample of peanut worm found in the fouling complex. (G) DP12H & DP13H: the sample of crab found in the fouling complex. (H) the sample of polychaete found in the fouling complex. (I) the sample of polychaete found in the fouling complex.

sensitive for divergent sequences. Indeed, it can better detect similarity among distantly related sequences than BLASTn.

When the results of BLASTx came out, the species names with the highest percent identity were searched to see the species the specimens belong to. The highest percent identity means 99% percentage ID for species while 98% or lower refers to only genus level or high level family or class.

4.3. Biofouling communities as brittle stars' habitat

Brittle stars are usually found in sea waters. Because of that in the wild, they eat dead planktons and bacteria that fall on the seabed. Because brittle stars are bottom dwellers, they survive and protect themselves from predators they bury in the seabed or hide in nooks and crevices they may find. Thus, brittle stars dwell in darker areas. Figure 2 shows this feature of brittle stars as they are clustered together under the light. As biofouling communities have

Figure 2. The brittle stars collected in Dapeng.

condensed area and gaps in between, it provides a preferable habitat for brittle stars.

4.4. Other species in biofouling communities

Besides the specimen of brittle star, we classified 8 other species from the biofouling community when we were using tweezers to separate different species: isopod, tube-worm, 3 kinds of polychaete, peanut worm, crab, amphipod. Isopods are a varied group. They often inhabit the ocean floor, with some species living in association with other organisms. They are the food sources for some fishes, birds, larger crustaceans and certain molluscs; tubeworms thrive in areas where mineral-rich fluids emerge from the seafloor. Tube worms face predation from specialized predators such as certain species of snails, crabs and fishes; polychaetas are a diverse class of annelid worms found in marine environments worldwide. Their habitat includes mud, sand and rock. They are prey for a wide range of animals including fishes, crabs, sea stars and other predatory marine invertebrates; peanut worm live in burrows in soft sediments on the seabed, often in shallow coastal waters. Their potential predators include fishes, crustaceans and some other marine mammals; crabs dwell in almost all marine and freshwater environments. They have a wide array of predators including fishes, birds, octopuses, marine mammals and larger

crustaceans; amphipods are found in both marine and freshwater environments. They are consumed by numerous organisms including fishes, birds, marine mammals and larger invertebrates.

Based on the species we have identified in biofouling communities; biofouling communities contribute to the overall biodiversity of marine environments. It is also important to note that microfoulers includes bacteria, archaea, fungi, microalgae and sessile metazoans [3], also constitute the rich species diversity in the biofouling communities. Moreover, biofouling communities provide habitat and food sources for a diverse array of organisms as the biofouling organisms are prey for bigger fishes and the biofouling communities also provide the organisms habitat. In terms of biofouling organisms, they can also serve as indicators of environmental health. Changes in biofouling community composition and abundance may signal shifts in water quality, substrate conditions, or broader ecological dynamics, offering valuable insights into ecosystem changes.

5. Conclusion

From the identification and classification of species living inside biofouling communities, the identified species play pivotal roles in both marine and industrial ecosystems. Based on the study, the species that dwell in biofouling communities are prey for big fishes or marine organisms. This means that the biofouling communities with these species attract fishes, which play a significant role in fishing industries. From enhancing shipping efficiency to contributing to pharmaceutical and biotechnology advancements, these communities offer numerous economic benefits. Hence, the significance of biofouling communities must be acknowledged.

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